

3-D EM inversion considering induced polarization effect

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SUMMARY

Modelling induced polarization (IP) effects in electromagnetic (EM) data is increasingly becoming a standard tool in mineral exploration, but the industry standard is still based on 1-D forward and Jacobian modelling. We have developed a 3-D electromagnetic forward and inversion method within the EEMverter modelling platform, incorporating IP effects. The 3-D computations are performed in the frequency domain using the vector finite element method and then transformed into the time domain via Hankel transformation. This approach enables modelling of any IP parametrization, ranging from the simple constant phase angle model to a full Debye decomposition. Furthermore, 3-D forward modelling mesh and inversion mesh are built independently: an Octree forward mesh is designed for efficient spatial segmentation for single or multiple soundings, while the inversion parameters are defined on a structured model mesh, which is linked to the forward meshes via interpolation. In conjunction with the development of a full 3-D EM-IP inversion, we introduce a novel 3-D inversion workflow. This workflow allows for hybrid 1-D-3-D computations, both sequentially and spatially, enabling 3-D modelling exclusively in the most significant and interesting areas of the survey. We tested the hybrid 1-D-3-D inversion workflow using airborne electromagnetic (AEM) data acquired by Xcalibur with the HeliTEM system in the Staré Ransko area (Czech Republic), known for its gabbro-peridotite rocks hosting nickel-copper ± cobalt, platinum group element (Ni-Cu ± Co, PGE) mineralization. The results demonstrate that the hybrid inversion effectively addresses the challenges of 3-D modelling on large-scale data sets. It enhances interpretation reliability in regions with strong 3-D effects and shows a significant spatial correlation between resistivity and chargeability phase anomalies and known mineral deposits. Moreover, both synthetic and field data indicate that the resistivity parameter is more sensitive to 3-D effects than the chargeability phase parameter.

Key words: Electromagnetic theory; Induced polarization; Finite element method; Inverse theory; Numerical modelling.

1 INTRODUCTION

Geophysical electromagnetic (EM) technology, including ground-based EM, airborne electromagnetic (AEM) and waterborne EM, recognized for its efficiency and flexibility, has been extensively applied in raw material mineral resource exploration (F. Dauti *et al.* 2024), hydrogeological mapping (Maurya *et al.* 2023) and geothermal exploration (Finn *et al.* 2022).

With advancements in data quality and expanding survey areas, researchers have observed inductive induced polarization (IP)

phenomena in raw material zones (Babu *et al.* 2017), clay layers (Hallbauer-Zadorozhnaya & Stettler 2006) and polar permafrost regions (Grombacher *et al.* 2021). These phenomena typically manifest as a sign reversal (SR) in the late-time gate of collected EM data. In high-resistivity backgrounds, this can even result in negative responses across all time gates (Lin *et al.* 2019). The SR mechanism (Flis *et al.* 1989) involves induced currents triggering reverse polarization currents in polarizable media during downward propagation. When polarization current density exceeds that of the induced currents, SR occurs. In weakly polarizable media, SR may

not occur but can still disrupt EM decay trends, biasing resistivity inversion. Consequently, to enhance the reliability of EM data interpretation and gain insights into the distribution of polarizable units in the subsurface, the IP effect is increasingly incorporated into EM data inversion.

The Cole–Cole relaxation model (Pelton *et al.* 1978) is the most widely used method to simulate the IP effect in electromagnetics. Scholars have conducted extensive research, spanning modelling (Ingeman-Nielsen & Baumgartner 2006; Kaminski & Viezzoli 2017; Viezzoli & Manca 2020), inversion applications (Kratzer & Macnae 2012; Seidel & Tezkan 2017) and uncertainty estimation (Davies *et al.* 2023). However, the strong correlation among Cole–Cole model parameters increases inversion non-uniqueness and complexity. To address this, Fiandaca *et al.* (2018) proposed a re-parametrized Cole–Cole model, which includes the maximum phase angle model (MPA), the maximum imaginary conductivity (MIC) model and the minimum imaginary resistivity (MIR) model. These models can reduce the correlation among polarization parameters, thereby improving the resolution of the inverted model parameters. Currently, the re-parametrized models have been successfully applied to various EM data sets, demonstrating superior performance (Lin *et al.* 2019; Junior *et al.* 2020; Grombacher *et al.* 2021; Maurya *et al.* 2022; Dauti *et al.* 2024). In general, modelling IP effects in EM data is becoming standard practice, particularly in mineral exploration. However, the industry standard is still grounded in 1-D forward and Jacobian modelling. In flat terrains with approximately layered subsurface geology, 1-D inversion can yield relatively accurate interpretations (Auken *et al.* 2008). Conversely, in rugged terrains with significant lateral variations in subsurface geology, such as mineral deposits, 1-D forward modelling becomes inadequate, necessitating 3-D inversion for accurate interpretation.

In recent years, research on 3-D EM modelling incorporating the IP effect has advanced (Marchant *et al.* 2014; Qi *et al.* 2019; Mörbe *et al.* 2024; Zhang *et al.* 2024), but publications on 3-D EM inversion accounting for IP effects remain limited. Kang & Oldenburg (2016 & 2018) proposed a strategy to decouple the IP effect from EM data and perform separate 3-D inversions. However, due to the nonlinear relationship between the IP effect and EM responses, true decoupling remains challenging. Cox *et al.* (2023, 2024) developed a full 3-D AEM inversion strategy using an integral equation approach and a generalized Cole–Cole model to simulate the IP effect. Nevertheless, due to serious equivalence problems and limitations in computational efficiency, applying 3-D EM inversion with IP effects to large-scale exploration data remains difficult. To address these challenges, we developed a full 3-D EM forward modelling and inversion strategy incorporating the IP effect based on the vector finite element (FE) method on the EEMverter platform (Fiandaca *et al.* 2024), with the following characteristics:

(i) A decoupled voxel mesh strategy (Fiandaca *et al.* 2013) defines distinct forward and inversion model meshes. The forward mesh uses an unstructured Octree mesh (Xiao *et al.* 2022), enabling easy local refinement in the footprint region.

(ii) The 3-D EM-IP inversion utilizes the MPA re-parametrization model, with the spectral parameters defined in two separate model meshes: resistivity and maximum phase angle are assigned to a 3-D mesh, while phase relaxation time and frequency exponent are assigned to a 2-D mesh that restricts variations to the horizontal plane, enhancing the sensitivity of the spectral parameters (Dauti *et al.* 2023).

(iii) The inversion employs a multicycle iterative strategy, supporting hybrid 1-D/3-D computations sequentially and spatially.

This allows 3-D modelling to be focused only on the most promising areas of large-scale surveys.

2 METHOD AND THEORY

2.1 Octree mesh

In our approach, independent meshes for forward modelling and inversion of EM data were designed using voxel mesh decoupling (Fig. 1c). Inversion parameters are defined on the nodes of a structured model mesh, which differs from the forward mesh in that its nodes are uniformly distributed horizontally and increase logarithmically vertically. These node values are linked to the forward mesh through spatial-distance-based interpolation functions. 3-D forward and Jacobian calculations utilize an Octree mesh. As shown in Figs 1(a) and (b), the Octree mesh consists of cubes of varying sizes, with a regularized structure that simplifies the determination of node and edge information for any spatial element. Additionally, the Octree mesh offers strong geometric flexibility, enabling local refinement or coarsening (Haber & Schwarzbach 2014). These features provide unique advantages in terrain simulation and footprint area refinement. For further details on Octree mesh design, refer to Xiao *et al.* (2022) and Han *et al.* (2022).

2.2 3-D Forward modelling

In our 3-D EM numerical simulation approach, we employ a primary–secondary field separation technique. Unlike the traditional total field computation, this method does not require dense meshing near the source and has a smaller footprint area (Zhang *et al.* 2021), conserving computational resources. By separating the primary field (\mathbf{E}^p) and the secondary field (\mathbf{E}^s), as well as the background conductivity (σ^p) and anomalous conductivity (σ^s), the Maxwell equations for the secondary field in the frequency domain can be expressed as:

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{E}^s = i\omega\mu\mathbf{H}^s, \quad (1)$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{H}^s = \sigma\mathbf{E}^s + \sigma^s\mathbf{E}^p, \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{H}^s is the secondary magnetic field; σ , μ and ω are the conductivity, permeability and the angular frequency, respectively. Taking a vector product of eq. (2) with shape functions \mathbf{N} (Jin 2015) and applying Dirichlet boundary conditions, the frequency domain electromagnetic curl–curl equation is:

$$f_{\Omega}(\nabla \times \mathbf{N} \cdot \nabla \times \mathbf{E}^s - i\omega\mu(\sigma^s + \sigma^p)\mathbf{N} \cdot \mathbf{E}^s) dV = f_{\Omega}(i\omega\mu\sigma^s\mathbf{N} \cdot \mathbf{E}^p) dV, \quad (3)$$

$$E_s|_{\Omega} = 0.$$

Using the concept of the finite element method, the computational domain is discretized into small elements, and the electric field within each element (\mathbf{E}^e) can be defined by its edge fields E_i^e :

$$\mathbf{E}^e = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{edge}}} \mathbf{N}_i^e E_i^e, \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{N}_i is the shape function at the i th edge. By combining the equations for all the elements, a linear sparse system of equations is thus formulated as:

$$\mathbf{K}\mathbf{E}^s = \mathbf{B}, \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{K} represents the sum of the stiffness matrix and the mass matrix. We use the direct solver PARDISO to solve eq. (5), thereby obtaining the edge electric field for all elements. The electric field at the receiver location is obtained through an interpolation function,

Figure 1. Diagram of Octree mesh and decoupled voxel mesh. (a) Quadtree mesh and representative trees; (b) Octree mesh refinement; (c) Decoupled voxel mesh.

and its magnetic field is calculated by Faraday's law. After obtaining the frequency domain response, the time domain response can be obtained by sine or cosine transformation through an Hankel transform, incorporating the receiver filter characteristics as well as the current waveform following Fitterman & Anderson (1987). Solving the differential equations in the frequency domain, instead of using time-stepping methods, allows for straightforward IP modelling by representing the conductivity in eq. (3) as complex conductivity. The classic Cole–Cole model can be expressed as (Pelton *et al.* 1978):

$$\sigma(\omega) = \frac{1}{\rho_0 \left[1 - \frac{m_0}{10^3} \left(1 - \frac{1}{1 + (i\omega\tau_\rho)^C} \right) \right]}, \quad (6)$$

where ρ_0 is the direct current resistivity ($\Omega \text{ m}$), m_0 is the intrinsic chargeability (mV V^{-1}), τ_ρ is the relaxation time (s), ω is the angular frequency and C is the frequency exponent. However, the strong correlation between m_0 and C increases inversion complexity. To address this, we employ the MPA re-parametrization model, which can reduce the correlation between polarization parameters and enhance inversion resolution (Fiandaca *et al.* 2018):

$$\mathbf{m}_{\text{MPA}} = \{\rho_0, \varphi_{\text{max}}, \tau_\varphi, C\}, \quad (7)$$

where φ_{max} represents the maximum phase angle (or chargeability phase) of the Cole–Cole complex conductivity and τ_φ is the inverse

of the frequency at which φ_{max} is reached. Among the MPA parameters, φ_{max} is the most effective parameter for evaluating the strength of the IP effect. To optimize parameter analysis and enhance inversion resolution of the primary IP parameters, we employed a dual-mesh inversion strategy. Here, ρ_0 and φ_{max} varied freely in 3-D space, while C and τ_φ were constrained to vary only in the planar direction, assuming they remain constant along the depth axis. This approach, validated in prior studies (Fiandaca *et al.* 2023; Dauti *et al.* 2024), improves inversion stability and resolution for resistivity and chargeability phase parameters. In this study, we focus exclusively on analysing the primary IP parameters ($\rho_0, \varphi_{\text{max}}$) within the MPA model. While the parameters τ_φ and C offer valuable insights into subsurface characteristics, we have excluded their analysis in the main text to maintain analytical focus. The corresponding inversion results for these parameters across both synthetic and field cases are presented in Appendix A.

2.3 Jacobian matrix and inversion

The Jacobian matrix quantifies how changes in model parameters (\mathbf{m}) affect the received response, that is,

$$J_i = \frac{\partial \mathbf{d}_i}{\partial \mathbf{m}}, \quad (8)$$

where \mathbf{d}_i is the EM response at the i th observation point. As we mentioned before, \mathbf{d} can be obtained by interpolating the secondary

Figure 2. Comparison of calculation accuracy between the frequency domain 3-D EM forward modelling and 1-D solutions. The first column (a) shows the PPM response values for the HCP configuration, the second column (b) shows the PPM response values for VCX configuration and the third column (c) shows the relative percentage error. From top to bottom, the three rows correspond to half-space resistivities of 1, 100 and 1000 Ω m, respectively.

electric field:

$$\mathbf{d}_i = \mathbf{L}_i^T \mathbf{E}_i^s, \quad (9)$$

where \mathbf{L}_i is the interpolation vector. Combining eqs (5), (8) and (9), it can be derived:

$$\mathbf{J}_i = \mathbf{L}_i^T \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}_i^s}{\partial \mathbf{m}} = \mathbf{L}_i^T \mathbf{K}_i^{-1} \frac{\partial \mathbf{K}_i}{\partial \mathbf{m}} (\mathbf{E}_i^p + \mathbf{E}_i^s), \quad (10)$$

The 3-D Jacobian of the model space \mathbf{J}_M is calculated by summing the contributions of all forward meshes within the footprint area, using the domain decomposition with a forward mesh for single or multiple soundings in 3-D EM computations (Cox *et al.* 2010), following the approach presented in Zhang *et al.* (2021). The total Jacobian is used for computing the inversion model in a Levenberg–Marquardt linearized approach as follows:

$$\mathbf{M}_{n+1,j} = \mathbf{M}_{n,j} + [\mathbf{J}_{M,j}^T \mathbf{C}_d^{-1} \mathbf{J}_{M,j} + \mathbf{R}^T \mathbf{C}_{R,j}^{-1} \mathbf{R}_j + \lambda \mathbf{I}]^{-1} \cdot [\mathbf{J}_{M,j}^T \mathbf{C}_d^{-1} \cdot (\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{f}_{n,j}) + \mathbf{R}^T \mathbf{C}_{R,j}^{-1} \mathbf{R}_j \cdot \mathbf{M}_{n,j}], \quad (11)$$

where \mathbf{d} and \mathbf{f}_n are the observed data and the forward modelling data, respectively, while \mathbf{C}_d and \mathbf{C}_R are the data covariance matrix and the model constraint covariance matrix, respectively. In eq. (11) the

subscript j indicates that the inversion process can be divided into multiple cycles, allowing adjustments in forward computation (e.g. transitioning from 1-D to 3-D) and modifications to the objective function by adding or removing data/constraints in each cycle j . To accelerate the convergence of the 3-D inversion, we initially set up a 1-D inversion cycle, followed by a 3-D (or hybrid 1-D-3-D) inversion cycle.

2.4 Accuracy check for forward modelling

To validate the accuracy of the 3-D forward modelling, we computed the 3-D response of a uniform half-space model in both the frequency and time domains, comparing the results with the 1-D solution. Similarly to our 3-D implementation, the 1-D forward response is computed in frequency domain (with a vertical magnetic dipole source) and subsequently transformed in time domain through a Hankel transform taking into account filters and current waveform, following Effersø *et al.* (1999).

Fig. 2 illustrates the accuracy verification of frequency domain (FD) numerical modelling across various frequencies. We evaluated

Figure 3. Comparison of the Jacobian accuracy between 3-D and 1-D frequency domain modelling. (a) Jacobian values at different frequencies; (b) Jacobian values at different resistivities. All Jacobian values are presented as absolute values.

Figure 4. Comparison of 3-D and 1-D time-domain EM Jacobian matrices and responses. The number of time gates is 29, the number of earth layers is set to 21 and the resistivity value is set to a uniform half-space of 100 Ω m.

two transceiver configurations: horizontal coplanar (HCP) and vertical coaxial (VCX). For the HCP configuration, the 3-D modelling error remained below 3 per cent within the frequency range of 10^2 to 10^6 Hz. In the VCX configuration, the error exceeded 3 per cent only under low-resistivity (1 Ω m) and high-frequency (10^6 Hz) conditions, suggesting that VCX requires enhanced mesh refinement in shallow conductive regions. Overall, the 3-D FD modelling results align well with the 1-D solution. Fig. 3 compares the Jacobian values from the 3-D forward modelling with those from the 1-D solution. The two Jacobian results show good consistency, with minor discrepancies observed at high frequencies. These discrepancies can be reduced by further refining the mesh.

Fig. 4 compares the 3-D time-domain (TD) EM Jacobian matrix with the 1-D Jacobian matrix, excluding the IP effect. The 1-D Jacobian matrix was computed using 29 time gates and 21 layers. For the 3-D Jacobian matrix, we summed the Jacobian values horizontally for each layer. Although the Octree mesh does not perfectly align with the layered earth, potentially introducing deviations, the results in Fig. 4 show strong agreement between the 3-D TD Jacobian matrix and the 1-D solution. The TD response calculations utilized both the sine transform (imaginary part of the FD field value) and the cosine transform (real part of the FD field value). The 3-D forward response obtained from both methods aligns well with the 1-D forward response. Specifically, the relative error for each time gate does not exceed 5 per cent for the sine transform and 6 per cent for the cosine transform. The sine transform demonstrates slightly higher accuracy in early time gates compared to the cosine transform.

Fig. 5 compares 3-D and 1-D Jacobian matrices, incorporating IP effects. The 3-D Jacobian matrix values for each polarization parameter align well with the 1-D Jacobian matrix. Under IP effects, the late-time TEM response exhibits SR. Both transformation methods show slightly increased calculation errors near the sign change point. Specifically, the sine transform's maximum error in the SR area exceeds 6 per cent, while errors in other time gates remain below 5 per cent. In contrast, the cosine transform's error near the sign change time gate exceeds 10 per cent. These errors in the SR area are acceptable, as the standard deviation (STD) of field data during SR is typically large. Due to its superior accuracy, the sine transform method is adopted as the default for subsequent 3-D modelling.

3 SYNTHETIC EXAMPLE

This section evaluates the performance of 3-D inversions by designing a synthetic model with IP anomalies. We compare the ability of a (i) resistivity-only inversion, (ii) 1-D MPA inversion and (iii) 3-D MPA inversion to recover the synthetic model. Each inversion is based on L2 norm minimization. To clearly present the inversion results, the model is configured as a 2-D survey line. The 3-D inversion for this survey line is executed in 2-D mode (using a 2-D model mesh), while forward modelling remains based on 3-D physics. The case of a 3-D model mesh will be addressed in the field data section.

As illustrated in Fig. 6(a), the 2-D geological model incorporates two low-resistivity and high-polarization anomalies (50 Ω m, 200 mrad) within a high-resistivity and weak-polarization background

Figure 5. Comparison of 3-D and 1-D time-domain EM Jacobian matrices and responses, incorporating the IP effect. The MPA reparametrization model was used to characterize the IP effect, with the following parameters: resistivity (ρ) = 100 Ω m, chargeability phase (Φ) = 200 mrad, phase relaxation time (T_{Φ}) = 0.01 s and frequency exponent (C) = 0.5.

(300 Ω m, 0.1 mrad). The anomalies are positioned on each side of the survey line between 34 and 83 m depth, and are separated by approximately 180 m. This model configuration allows us to evaluate whether the presence of adjacent anomalies in the subsurface can induce 3-D effects and the consequent impact on the inversion of IP parameters. We employed 3-D forward modelling to compute the EM response of the geological model. Noise was not introduced into the data to isolate the 3-D effects on the anomaly distribution recovered in the subsequent inversion process. The STD of the data was set to 5 per cent (Auken *et al.* 2008). In the event of an SR, the EEMverter automatically increases the STD for the time gates near the SR to ensure inversion stability.

Fig. 7(a) illustrates the 3-D forward modelling AEM data for the model. The data clearly shows a significant SR phenomenon caused by the IP anomalies on both sides. Due to 3-D effects, the SR phenomenon is not only observed directly above the IP anomalies but also appears in the area between them.

Figs 6(b) to (g) show the results of 1-D MPA inversion, resistivity-only inversion and 3-D MPA inversion, respectively. Because the resistivity-only inversion cannot process negative data, such data is treated as noise and excluded during the inversion. Using this approach, an arcuate low-resistivity anomaly zone forms near the IP anomalies, and a highly conductive spurious anomaly appears between them. Furthermore, the resistivity values in the deep part of the model were overestimated, and the depth of investigation (DOI) near the IP anomalies was notably reduced due to the removal of negative data responses. After incorporating the IP effect, the resistivity results from the 1-D MPA inversion demonstrated improvements in both the spatial distribution of subsurface IP anomalies and the DOI range, although the 3-D arcuate effect remains significant. Fig. 6(f) illustrates the 1-D MPA inversion results, showing a continuous strong chargeability phase anomaly near the IP anomaly. Although the inversion underestimated the IP anomaly's position, it did not exhibit the strong 3-D arcuate effect seen in the resistivity results. In

Figure 6. Inversion results for IP anomalies using different inversion methods. (a) True resistivity model; (b) Resistivity model from 1-D MPA inversion; (c) Resistivity model from 1-D resistivity-only inversion; (d) Resistivity model from 3-D MPA inversion; (e) True Phi model; (f) Phi model from 1-D MPA inversion; (g) Phi model from 3-D MPA inversion.

contrast, the 3-D MPA inversion significantly improves the imaging accuracy of the low-resistivity anomaly, removes the arc effect and delivers sharper boundaries for the IP parameters.

Fig. 7 shows the data fitting results for the three inversion methods. While all methods achieved good overall fitting, the 3-D MPA inversion achieved the best data fit. The resistivity-only inversion removed negative responses but still performed poorly for time gates strongly influenced by the IP effect. The 1-D MPA inversion improved fitting accuracy in regions with strong IP effects but slightly degraded in negative response time gates where 3-D effects were significant.

In summary, when polarizable anomalies are present underground, inversion methods that incorporate IP effects improve the reliability of the results. These methods not only deliver resistivity distributions but also provide polarization parameter information, enabling more accurate geological interpretations. However, when

significant geological 3-D effects are present in the observed data, 1-D inversion methods tend to produce spurious anomalies. In such scenarios, 3-D inversion can further enhance result reliability and improve model boundary resolution. Additionally, the synthetic results indicate that resistivity parameters are more sensitive to 3-D effects than chargeability phase parameters.

4 APPLICATION TO AEM DATA

4.1 AEM data

The Ransko gabbro-peridotite massif, located in the easternmost part of the European Variscan Orogen in Eastern Bohemia, hosts smaller scale semimassive to disseminated magmatic nickel-copper \pm cobalt and platinum group element (Ni-Cu \pm Co, PGE)

Figure 7. Inversion misfit comparison. (a) 3-D EM forward modelling data; (b) True model; (c) The fitting quality of single sounding data; (d), (e) and (f) respectively show the data fitting quality for all time gates using the 1-D resistivity-only inversion, 1-D MPA inversion and 3-D MPA inversion.

mineralization. This mineralization is predominantly developed near the contact zones between olivine-enriched rocks and gabbro (Ackerman *et al.* 2013, 2025).

Additionally, zinc-copper (Zn-Cu) ore bodies are associated with small quartz diorite intrusions (Němec & Holub 1980). Some geological and geochemical studies indicate that the main mineralized zones are situated at depths of 150 to 250 m (Pašava *et al.* 2003; Pertoldová *et al.* 2010; Haluzová *et al.* 2015). To explore potential mineralization areas, large-scale airborne AEM surveys were conducted within the SEMACRET Horizon Europe project, focusing on Ni-Cu mineralization. The data were acquired by Xcalibur Smart Mapping with the latest iteration of the HeliTEM system (Smiarowski *et al.* 2018), with 12.5 Hz base frequency. Fig. 8 displays the HeliTEM survey lines and a portion of the data. Notably, some late time gate data exhibit a clear SR phenomenon, necessitating dispersion-resistivity modelling.

4.2 Inversion results

Given the large-scale nature of the Ransko AEM survey, which includes over 14 000 measurement soundings, full 3-D inversion would be computationally intensive and prone to memory limitations. To balance efficiency and reliability, an innovative hybrid 1-D-3-D inversion strategy was developed. This approach involves three iterative cycles: (i) an initial autostart cycle using a single-layer 1-D forward mesh to determine the best starting model without vertical parameter variability; (ii) a second cycle employing

1-D forward and Jacobian computations and (iii) a final cycle transitioning to 3-D forward and Jacobian calculations for soundings in areas of interest or regions with significant electrical property contrasts.

Fig. 9 presents the inversion model of the AEM data obtained using the hybrid 1-D-3-D approach, displaying resistivity and chargeability phase and sounding positions. Within the primary mineralized zone, 1800 soundings were modelled in 3-D (orange dots in Fig. 8), while the remaining 12 500 soundings were modelled in 1-D (yellow dots). The 1800 soundings were divided into 60 groups (tessellating the modelled area with 300 m × 300 m tiles), each group modelled with an independent octree mesh. Notably, the inversion model in Fig. 9 shows no evident artefacts, either within the 3-D-modelled areas across octree meshes or at the boundaries between 1-D and 3-D computations, demonstrating the robustness of the domain decomposition approach.

Fig. 10(a) presents the 150 m depth slice of resistivity and chargeability phase models, alongside known Zn-Cu and Ni-Cu deposits. It reveals that most mineralization is concentrated along the margins of high-Phi zones, which also display significant lateral resistivity variations. At a greater depth of 250 m (Fig. 10b), the high-Phi zones become more sharply defined, and the conductive zone shows a coherent downward extension consistent with the shallower slice. Potential mineral occurrences at this depth are spatially linked to the conductive zones and the boundaries of the strongest chargeability anomalies.

Fig. 11(a) displays the spatial distribution of a geological cross-section in the study area (marked by the magenta line), along with

Figure 8. Airborne survey lines were conducted over the Staré Ransko area. Dark yellow represents all AEM survey lines, while orange highlights the concentrated zones of Zn-Cu and Ni-Cu mineralization, where data are modelled in 3-D. The black line marks the position of the example data stripe shown. Within the data stripe, negative recordings linked to IP effects are shown in red, positive recordings in blue and manually removed noise in grey.

Figure 9. Hybrid 1-D-3-D inversion of Staré Ransko AEM data. Top: central part of the Octree mesh for 3-D computation and corresponding soundings (white dots) through domain decomposition, with (a) resistivity and (b) Phi values. Bottom: vertical sections of the inversion model showing the resistivity and Phi parameters (down to a depth of 700 m). A detailed zoomed-in view of the 3-D inversion area is provided at the bottom.

Figure 10. Comparison between the hybrid 1-D-3-D inversion depth sections and known mineralized zones. (a) AEM resistivity (top) and chargeability phase (bottom) depth slices at 130–170 m depth; (b) AEM resistivity (top) and chargeability phase (bottom) depth slices at 215–275 m depth.

its correlation to AEM sounding locations. The purple dashed line delineates the spatial distribution of known deposits within the geological section. A comparative analysis of 1-D-only inversion and hybrid 1-D-3-D inversion along the same profile (Figs 11b and c) reveals that both methods generate similar overall patterns in resistivity and chargeability phase. However, the hybrid approach improves the definition of the anomaly's geometry. Notably, the 3-D inversion results show more pronounced variations in resistivity compared to chargeability phase values. This further confirms that the resistivity parameter is more sensitive to 3-D effects than the chargeability phase parameter. Once again, the transition between the 1-D and 3-D portions of the modelling along the section remains seamless.

Figs 12(a) and (b) compare the misfit between the 1-D-only inversion and the hybrid 1-D-3-D inversion strategies. The hybrid method exhibits slightly higher misfit values in 3-D-modelled regions, particularly near domain boundaries. This is primarily attributed to the difficulty of simultaneously satisfying both 1-D and 3-D physical constraints in these transitional zones. Although the 1-D inversion yields better-fitting models (as it does not account for 3-D effects), these results are less reliable in geologically complex areas where 3-D effects are significant. Fig. 12(c) illustrates the misfit evolution through three distinct inversion cycles. The initial 1-D inversion cycle achieved a baseline misfit of 0.92, while the subsequent transition to hybrid 1-D-3-D modelling resulted in a significant misfit increase to 2.70—this dramatic rise clearly demonstrates the 3-D effects present in the deposit-concentrated zones. The final hybrid inversion successfully reduced the misfit to 1.18, representing a 56 per cent improvement ($2.70 - 1.18 / 2.70$) from the initial hybrid result and confirming enhanced model reliability for deposit-rich areas under 3-D physical constraints. All inversions were executed on a Windows Server 2019 system, equipped with an AMD EPYC 7763 64-Core Processor (2.45 GHz) and 1 TB RAM configuration.

The hybrid 1-D-3-D inversion process requires approximately 10 hr of computation time per iteration. In this study, the 3-D modelling area comprises a total of 1800 soundings, and 51 frequencies were utilized for the frequency–time transformation. This translates to a single iteration solving time of approximately 0.4 s per sounding for the 3-D frequency-domain electromagnetic field equations. In comparison, each iteration of 1-D-only inversion requires approximately 0.2 hr. The efficiency of the hybrid 1-D-3-D inversion, compared to full 3-D-only inversion, is directly influenced by the size of the 3-D modelling domain. In the Ransko field data case, the time required to execute 3-D-only inversion can be estimated to be approximately eight times that of the hybrid 1-D-3-D inversion strategy. Figs 12(d)–(g) present the data fitting results from the hybrid 1-D-3-D inversion, showcasing four representative survey lines and several survey points within the 3-D domain. The visualization uses transparent orange shading to demarcate 3-D inversion zones, contrasting with adjacent 1-D inversion areas. The results demonstrate robust overall fitting quality, with only localized increases in misfit in transitional boundary zones (e.g. Line 10 780), resulting from dimensional changes in the forward modelling kernel. These localized discrepancies do not affect the spatial continuity of the inversion model or the geological interpretability across domain boundaries, confirming the interpretive stability of this hybrid inversion approach.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Most mineral deposits exhibit chargeability, leading to the presence of IP effects in the acquired EM data. Currently, the industrial standard for EM data processing relies primarily on 1-D inversion techniques that incorporate IP effects. While 1-D EM-IP inversion significantly improves data fitting compared to resistivity-only

Figure 11. AEM resistivity and chargeability phase comparison with a geological cross-section. (a) Geological cross-section marked by the magenta line; (b) From top to bottom: hybrid 1-D-3-D resistivity model, 1-D-only resistivity model and 3-D/1-D resistivity ratio; (c) From top to bottom: hybrid 1-D-3-D chargeability phase, 1-D-only chargeability phase, and 3-D/1-D chargeability phase ratio.

inversion and offers insights into subsurface IP parameter distribution, our synthetic case studies show that 1-D inversion struggles to produce reliable subsurface models in the presence of strong 3-D effects from subsurface anomalies. Although 3-D inversion is generally more time-consuming than 1-D inversion, the EEMverter platform's multicycle inversion framework offers a practical solution: the 3-D-1-D hybrid inversion strategy. This method leverages kernels of different dimensionality (3-D and 1-D), utilizing independent forward meshes and a shared model mesh. This approach enables inversion of large data sets while ensuring seamless transitions between 3-D and 1-D modelled areas.

We validated the feasibility of this strategy using AEM data from the Ransko gabbro-peridotite Massif in the Czech Republic. The 3-D-1-D hybrid inversion, which incorporates IP effects, demonstrates a strong correlation between known mineralization

and both resistivity and chargeability phase. By integrating resistivity and polarization parameters, mineral exploration can achieve greater reliability in identifying enriched mineral deposits. Our hybrid 1-D-3-D inversion results reveal that the ore body distribution within the Ransko Massif area potentially extends obliquely beyond the currently known mineralized zones on both flanks. This interpretation is supported by the presence of strong polarization parameters and favourable conductivity characteristics observed on both flanks. Additionally, both synthetic and field data analyses consistently demonstrate that the resistivity parameter is more sensitive to 3-D effects compared to the chargeability phase parameter. This underscores the importance of using 3-D modelling to interpret electromagnetic data in geologically complex terrains, particularly in areas with significant 3-D effects, irrespective of the presence or absence of IP effects. While this study does not provide a

Figure 12. Data misfit for hybrid 1-D-3-D inversion results. (a) Misfit for 1-D MPA inversion; (b) Misfit for hybrid 3-D and 1-D MPA inversion; (c) Three cycle inversion iterations; (d), (e), (f) and (g) show the data fit for four survey lines. The transparent orange area represents regions modelled in 3-D, while blue and red dots denote positive and negative observed data, respectively. The black line corresponds to the forward response of the inversion model.

detailed analysis of the relaxation time (τ_φ) and frequency exponent (C) parameters in the MPA inversion framework, our field-based case study results demonstrate that these parameters also hold significant value for mineral exploration. Specifically, the τ_φ parameter exhibits high sensitivity to the spatial distribution of mineral anomalies and 3-D effects, which will be a key focus of our future research.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Supplementary data are available at [GJRRS](https://academic.oup.com/gj/article/24/4/1/ggaf4628323/168) online.

Figure S1. Parameters C and τ_φ from the MPA inversion results in the synthetic data case. (a) True C model and results from 1-D and 3-D inversions; (b) True τ_φ model and results from 1-D and 3-D inversions.

Figure S2. Parameters C and τ_ϕ from the MPA inversion results in the field data case. (a) 1-D-only inversion; (b) Hybrid 1-D-3-D inversion.

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DATA AVAILABILITY

The airborne electromagnetic data used in this study are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17117648> (Chen *et al.* 2025).

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APPENDIX A: RELAXATION TIME (τ_φ) AND FREQUENCY EXPONENT (C) RESULTS

This appendix presents the maximum phase angle (MPA) inversion results for parameters C and τ_φ corresponding to both synthetic and field data cases discussed in the main text. As introduced before, to enhance the stability of the MPA inversion, C and τ_φ are constrained to vary only in the horizontal plane, maintaining constant values along the depth axis. Figs S1 and S2 present the 1-D and 3-D inversion results for parameters C and τ_φ , corresponding to the synthetic case and the field data case, respectively.

As illustrated in Fig. S2, the τ_φ and C values derived from the hybrid 1-D-3-D MPA inversion results exhibit no significant artefacts. However, a localized discontinuity of the anomaly is observed at the right boundary of the τ_φ parameter. Under higher C values, the τ_φ parameter demonstrates enhanced resolution in the inversion results. Furthermore, the τ_φ parameter in the hybrid inversion results shows more pronounced variations compared to the 1-D-only inversion results in known mineralized zones. This indicates that the τ_φ parameter is not only valuable for mineral exploration but also highly sensitive to 3-D effects, which will be a key focus of our future research.